

Research article

Provision of Healthcare Facilities In Douala: A Geographical Analysis

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Abstract

Background: Douala, Cameroon's largest city, faces persistent healthcare access challenges rooted in rapid, unplanned urban growth. Despite a high concentration of medical facilities and personnel, infrastructure development has not kept pace with population expansion, resulting in spatial inequities that disproportionately affect vulnerable communities.

Objectives: This study maps and analyzes the distribution of four healthcare provider types - public, private (for-profit and non-profit), traditional, and alternative - across Douala's urban landscape. It evaluates geographic equity in access across neighborhoods and socio-economic groups using a mixed-methods approach.

Methods: Healthcare facilities were mapped using GPS data and official records, while informal providers were identified through community-guided sampling. Spatial analysis in ArcGIS Pro included kernel density estimation, network analysis, and service area delineation based on a 30-minute travel time threshold. A spatial equity index was developed by integrating facility counts, population density, and accessibility metrics. Qualitative interviews with health officials, providers, and residents added contextual depth through thematic analysis.

Results: Findings revealed a concentration of facilities in central urban zones, with peripheral areas underserved. Public sector coverage was inadequate relative to population needs, while private providers dominated wealthier districts. Traditional and alternative practitioners filled critical gaps in informal settlements. Many residents in outlying areas exceeded the 30-minute travel threshold to formal care.

Conclusion: The study underscores the need for equitable urban health planning, recommending targeted expansion of public services and strategic integration of diverse provider types to improve coverage across Douala's diverse urban landscape.

1. Introduction

Douala, the bustling economic heart of Cameroon, stands as a testament to the nation's rapid urbanization. With a population exceeding three million, the city serves as a crucial hub for trade, industry, and commerce, attracting a continuous influx of people seeking economic opportunities and a better quality of life. This demographic explosion, however, places immense pressure on the city's infrastructure and public services, particularly the healthcare system. The provision of quality health care, defined as the availability of appropriate care to patients at the right time and in the right place, is intrinsically linked to the presence of adequate health care facilities [1]. These facilities are the fundamental settings where health care professionals and services are delivered, and their quality is a function of factors such as the presence of qualified staff, well-maintained medical equipment, accurate medical records, and efficient communication mechanisms among

practitioners and health institutions [2]. The effectiveness of a health care system is often measured by its ability to meet the population's needs, which is increasingly challenging in rapidly urbanizing regions where infrastructure development lags behind demographic expansion [3]. While Douala undeniably possesses a greater concentration of medical facilities, qualified personnel, and advanced medical technologies compared to Cameroon's rural hinterlands, the sheer scale of its population and the unplanned nature of its growth create a unique set of challenges. The establishment of health care infrastructures is often not keeping pace with the city's demographic and spatial growth. This creates a scenario where, despite the city being an object of a multitude of health care services, significant gaps and inequities in provision persist. The spatial distribution of healthcare facilities is often uneven, leading to significant disparities in access for different neighborhoods and socioeconomic groups. Furthermore, issues such as traffic congestion, inadequate public transport, and the concentration of poverty in specific areas can act as major barriers to healthcare access, even when a facility is geographically close. This article, therefore, undertakes a geographical analysis of healthcare provision in Douala, moving beyond a simple count of facilities to critically examine their spatial distribution, accessibility, and the implications for equitable healthcare for all of its residents. In this study, the provision of health care facilities in the city of Douala will be classified under four main categories: (a) Public sector health facilities, (b) Private for-profit and non-profit sector healthcare facilities, (c) Traditional healthcare facilities and (d) Alternative health care facilities. By mapping the landscape of healthcare in Douala and analyzing these different types of providers, this study seeks to highlight existing gaps and inform strategies for a more balanced and effective healthcare system in one of Africa's fastest-growing metropolises.

Literature Review

This literature review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of existing research on health care provision in rapidly urbanizing environments, drawing on scholarly work relevant to the challenges faced by cities like Douala. It will explore the theoretical frameworks, empirical studies, and policy implications related to the spatial distribution, accessibility, and quality of health care services in such contexts. The review will be structured to support the geographical analysis proposed in the introduction, specifically addressing the classification of health care facilities and the implications for equitable access.

The Urbanization-Health Nexus Theoretical Frameworks: The relationship between urbanization and health is a well-established area of research, with several theoretical models attempting to explain the complex dynamics at play. The urban health penalty model suggests that while urban areas may offer better access to services, they also expose residents to a unique set of health risks, including pollution, crime, and social stress, which can lead to poorer health outcomes for certain populations [4]. Conversely, the urban health advantage model posits that the concentration of resources, including health care facilities, in cities ultimately leads to better health outcomes compared to rural areas [4]. A more nuanced perspective, however, is the urban health equity framework, which recognizes that neither a universal penalty nor a universal advantage exists. Instead, it emphasizes that health outcomes and access to care are highly dependent on socioeconomic status, neighborhood characteristics, and the spatial distribution of services within the city [5]. This framework is particularly relevant to the study of Douala, as it highlights the importance of analyzing intra-urban disparities in health care provision.

Spatial Distribution and Accessibility of Health Care Facilities: A significant body of literature focuses on the spatial analysis of health care facilities, examining how their distribution impacts accessibility and equity. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have become a cornerstone of this research, allowing for the mapping and analysis of service locations in relation to population density, socioeconomic data, and transportation networks [6]. Studies in various rapidly urbanizing cities have consistently revealed uneven spatial distribution, with a higher concentration of facilities in affluent, centrally located areas and a scarcity in peripheral, low-income neighborhoods [7]. This unevenness is often a result of market forces, where private providers choose locations based on profitability rather than public health need. Research also highlights the importance of distinguishing between geographic accessibility (physical distance to a facility) and socioeconomic accessibility (the ability to afford and utilize services) [8]. The introduction's mention of traffic congestion and inadequate transport in Douala directly aligns with this literature, suggesting that geographical proximity does not guarantee functional accessibility.

The Role of Informal and Alternative Health Care Providers: The study's classification of health care facilities into public, private, traditional and alternative is crucial and well-supported by the literature on health systems in developing countries. Private and clandestine health care providers, such as unlicensed clinics, street vendors of medicine, and traditional healers, play a significant role in filling gaps left by the public sector, particularly in marginalized urban communities [9]. Research on this topic often explores the reasons for their prevalence, including affordability, cultural relevance, and perceived greater accessibility compared to public facilities [10]. However, this literature also raises significant concerns about the quality and safety of care provided by these informal actors. Lack of regulation and oversight can lead to misdiagnosis, inappropriate treatment, and the spread of infectious diseases, posing a substantial public health risk [11]. The study's analysis of this sector in Douala will contribute to a growing body of knowledge on the dual-edged nature of informal health care provision in urban Africa.

Policy and Planning Implications for Equitable Health Care Provision: The literature offers several policy recommendations for addressing health care inequities in rapidly growing cities. Strategic health facility planning is a key theme, advocating for a shift from reactive to proactive approaches in infrastructure development [12]. This includes using demographic projections and spatial analysis to anticipate future health needs and guide the location of new facilities. Furthermore, scholars emphasize the need for integrated urban planning, where health considerations are incorporated into decisions about housing, transport, and economic development [13]. For a city like Douala, this would mean coordinating the expansion of health care facilities with the development of public transport routes and the zoning of new residential areas. Finally, research points to the importance of regulating and engaging with the informal health sector rather than simply trying to eliminate it. This could involve training and certifying informal providers, integrating traditional medicine into the formal system, and raising public awareness about the risks and benefits of different types of care [9, 10]. This study's findings on the distribution and types of facilities in Douala can inform such policy interventions, aiming for a more inclusive and effective health system for all residents.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Data Collection

A multi-stage process was employed to gather both spatially grounded quantitative data and rich qualitative insights, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of healthcare provision across Douala. The initial phase involved compiling a detailed database of formal healthcare facilities using official records from the Littoral Regional Delegation of Public Health and the National Order of Physicians. Each facility's location was geocoded with high-precision GPS and cross-verified using satellite imagery to ensure spatial accuracy. To capture the presence of informal and traditional providers, who often operate outside formal regulatory frameworks, a purposive sampling strategy was adopted. Field researchers, guided by key informants such as community leaders, traditional healers' associations, and community health workers, systematically identified and recorded the geographic coordinates of these facilities across various neighborhoods. Complementing this spatial data, demographic and socioeconomic information was sourced from the most recent census conducted by the National Institute of Statistics (NIS) of Cameroon. Additional layers, including Douala's digital road network and administrative boundaries, were obtained from municipal and national authorities to support spatial analysis. To enrich the quantitative findings with lived experiences and contextual depth, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a diverse group of stakeholders. These included health officials from the Ministry of Public Health and regional delegations, healthcare providers spanning formal, informal, and traditional sectors, and community members representing various socioeconomic backgrounds and neighborhoods. Their perspectives offered valuable insights into healthcare-seeking behaviors, perceived barriers to access, and the operational realities of different facility types.

2.2. Data Processing and Analysis

To transform the raw data into meaningful insights, a combination of spatial and thematic techniques was employed, allowing for both quantitative precision and qualitative depth. All geospatial information collected during fieldwork was integrated into a Geographic Information System (GIS) database using ArcGIS Pro, forming the foundation for a series of spatial analyses. The distribution of healthcare facilities across Douala was first visualized through point mapping, followed by Kernel Density Estimation to highlight zones of high and low facility concentration. Although network analysis tools within ArcGIS Pro were employed to estimate travel times from the centroid of each quarter to the nearest formal healthcare facility, the automated approach did not adequately reflect the realities of Douala's urban landscape. Factors such as the city's unplanned development, varied topography, and inconsistent road conditions introduced limitations to purely model-based assessments. To address this, travel times and distances were refined through field inquiries, interviews, and direct observation, ensuring that the accessibility analysis aligned more closely with lived experiences. Service areas were delineated based on a 30-minute travel time threshold, offering a clearer picture of population coverage for each facility type. To evaluate equity in healthcare provision, a spatial equity index was developed by integrating facility counts, population density, and travel time metrics across administrative units. This enabled the identification of areas experiencing significant disparities in access to care. Complementing the spatial analysis, qualitative data from interviews were subjected to thematic analysis. Transcripts were carefully reviewed to identify recurring concepts related to healthcare access, quality, and decision-making. These initial codes were then grouped into broader themes such as barriers to access, trust in providers, and affordability of care. The themes were refined to ensure they accurately reflected the lived experiences of participants and aligned with the study's research objectives. Bringing both strands of analysis together, the final stage involved synthesizing spatial patterns with contextual narratives. For example, areas with a high concentration of informal facilities were examined alongside interview data from residents in those neighborhoods, revealing underlying drivers such as economic constraints and cultural preferences. This integrated approach provided a nuanced understanding of healthcare dynamics in Douala and informed the development of targeted, evidence-based policy recommendations aimed at promoting equitable access for all.

3. Results

3.1. An Urban Healthcare System Modeled on the National Framework

Cameroon's healthcare system is formally organized into a three-tiered pyramid that reflects the country's administrative divisions. This structure - central, intermediate, and peripheral - defines the flow of authority, resources, and service delivery across the nation.

- At the **central level**, the Ministry of Public Health (MINSANTE) oversees national policy and regulation. Institutions such as the Douala General Hospital and Yaoundé Central Hospital provide highly specialized care and serve as teaching and research centers.
- The **intermediate level** corresponds to Cameroon's ten administrative regions. Regional Public Health Delegations (DRSP) offer technical support to health districts and manage referral hospitals that bridge the gap between primary and tertiary care.
- At the **peripheral level**, the system becomes operational. Health districts implement national programs through District Hospitals, Medical Centers, and Integrated Health Centers - facilities designed to be the first point of contact for most citizens.

While this structure is intended to promote decentralized, community-based care - especially following the Alma-Ata Declaration of 1978 - the reality is more rigid. Centralized control often undermines local responsiveness, creating a disconnect between policy intentions and on-the-ground implementation. This tension is especially visible in urban settings like Douala, where the complexity of city life demands more flexible and adaptive health strategies.

3.2. The Urban Health Penalty: A Disparity in Provision

Douala's health system mirrors the national model but is shaped by the city's unique urban dynamics. On paper, the city appears well-resourced, hosting 17% of Cameroon's health facilities and 76% of those in the Littoral region. However, this quantitative abundance masks critical qualitative and spatial deficits. A striking imbalance exists between public and private provision. An overwhelming 94% of Douala's

Cameroon Healthcare System Pyramid

Figure 1: Cameroon Healthcare System

health facilities are privately operated, leaving the public sector with just 6%. This translates to only one public health center for every 55,245 residents. While private clinics often offer high-quality services, their unregulated fees make them inaccessible to many, forcing low-income populations to rely on overcrowded public facilities. Spatial analysis reveals further inequities. Public health services are concentrated in central and affluent districts, while informal settlements on the city’s periphery remain underserved. Poor road infrastructure exacerbates the problem - residents in these areas may face travel times exceeding an hour just to reach a referral center. These geographic and financial barriers push many toward informal and unregulated providers, whose practices, while often culturally resonant and affordable, pose risks to patient safety due to lack of oversight.

3.3. An urban health care system grouped into 4 sectors

Figure 2: Urban health care system

Public sector health facilities

This sector, controlled and managed by the state, includes all government-owned hospitals and health structures. Public health centers are intended to provide affordable, accessible care, but they are often hampered by insufficient funding and overcrowding. In Douala, a total of 55 public sector health facilities operate across the city, reflecting the state’s commitment to service provision despite persistent resource constraints. The public healthcare system in Cameroon is structured as a pyramid, designed to provide tiered access to medical services from the community level up to highly specialized care. This model is based on a three-tiered administrative system: the Central Level (the Ministry of Public Health), the Intermediate Level (Regional and Divisional Health Delegations), and the Peripheral Level (Health Districts).

This structure is mirrored in the public health facilities of Douala. The different categories of public health facilities are classified based on their level of care and referral capacity.

The spatial distribution of these public facilities in Douala is highly uneven and often reflects historical and socio-economic factors. While the national system is based on the principle of a decentralized "health district," the rapid and largely unplanned urbanization of Douala has led to significant geographical inequities. Below is a breakdown of the spatial analysis for each category,

- Category 1 Hospitals (General Hospitals) in Douala:** Douala has two Category 1 public hospitals offering the highest level of specialized care: Douala General Hospital, located in Malengue (Douala V) near planned neighborhoods like Makepe and Bonamoussadi, and Hôpital Gynéco-Obstétrique et Pédiatrique de Douala (HGOPEd), situated in Ngodi Bakoko (Douala III) on the city's eastern outskirts. While these hospitals serve as key referral centers, their limited number and peripheral locations highlight a mismatch between advanced healthcare services and the spatial realities of Douala's expanding urban population, especially for residents in informal or underserved areas.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of category 1 Hospitals in Douala

- Category 2 Hospitals in Douala:** In Douala, the urban healthcare landscape is anchored by a single Category 2 hospital: Hôpital Laquintinie, located in the heart of the city's central district, Akwa. As one of Cameroon's designated Central hospital, Laquintinie plays a pivotal role in the public health system, offering specialized and referral-level care to a rapidly growing urban population. Its strategic placement in a high-density, centrally accessible area reflects national planning priorities aimed at maximizing reach and efficiency.

Figure 4: Spatial location of category 2 Hospital in Douala

- Category 3 Hospitals (Regional Hospitals):** Although Category 3 hospitals – Regional hospitals - play a vital role in Cameroon’s healthcare system, none are currently located within the city of Douala. These regional hospitals are typically situated outside the city, serving broader administrative zones. Within Douala, healthcare provision relies instead on Category 1 and 2 hospitals, district-level facilities (Category 4), and a dense network of private and informal providers.
- Category 4 Hospitals (District Hospitals):** Douala has seven District Hospitals serving its nine urban districts, creating a clear gap in public healthcare coverage. These facilities - primarily located in central areas such as Deido, Bonassama, and Nylon - are intended to provide first-line care at the peripheral level. However, their concentration near the city center makes them less accessible to residents in outlying and informal settlements, who face financial and geographic barriers to care. As the city continues to expand rapidly and often without formal planning, these hospitals are increasingly overwhelmed by patients from underserved neighborhoods. The result is overcrowding, resource strain, and reduced service quality. This imbalance highlights the urgent need for a more equitable and geographically distributed healthcare infrastructure across Douala. Figure 5 illustrates the spatial distribution of these seven District Hospitals, highlighting the coverage gaps and reinforcing the need for strategic expansion to better serve the city’s growing population.

Figure 5: Spatial distribution of category 4 Hospitals in Douala

- Category 5 hospitals (Subdivisional Medical Centers) in Douala:** Subdivisional Medical Centers are designed to provide essential healthcare services at the subdivision level, serving as a critical link between Integrated Health Centers and District Hospitals. In Douala, a total of 36 such facilities were identified during fieldwork, though they vary significantly in terms of size, infrastructure, and available equipment. This uneven standard reflects broader disparities in resource allocation and operational capacity across the city. Their distribution plays a strategic role in addressing the healthcare needs of specific sub-populations, particularly in areas underserved by higher-tier facilities. Figure 6 shows the geographical location of these Subdivisional Medical Centers, highlighting both their spatial coverage and the gaps that persist in reaching vulnerable communities.

Figure 6: Spatial distribution of Category 5 Hospitals in Douala

- Category 6 (Integrated Health Centers) in Douala:** Integrated Health Centers represent the most basic tier of public healthcare infrastructure, designed to deliver primary health services directly to local communities. In Douala, only six such centers were identified, making them notably scarce relative to the city's population and geographic spread. While these facilities are intended to serve as accessible entry points into the health system, their placement is often concentrated in well-established, planned neighborhoods. This uneven distribution creates a pronounced spatial deficit, particularly in Douala's rapidly expanding informal settlements, where residents face significant barriers to accessing even the most basic care. Figure 7 below illustrates the location of these six Integrated Health Centers, highlighting their wide dispersion across the city and underscoring the need for more equitable placement to meet the demands of underserved populations.

Figure 7: Spatial distribution of category 6 Hospitals in Douala

- Category 7 (Ambulatory Health Centers):** Ambulatory Health Centers in Douala are predominantly shaped by the private sector, with the majority of facilities operating as private clinics or polyclinics offering outpatient services and basic consultations. While some public-private partnerships and smaller government-run centers exist, their presence is minimal. Only three ambulatory health centers were identified as publicly operated during fieldwork, underscoring the limited role of the public sector in this category. The geographic distribution of these facilities is critical, as they are intended to provide accessible, non-hospital-based care across the city. However, their concentration in more affluent or centrally located areas often leaves peripheral and low-income neighborhoods underserved Figure 8.

Figure 8: Spatial distribution of category 7 Hospitals in Douala

Public sector health facilities in Douala reflect Cameroon's national healthcare structure but reveal significant gaps in coverage and accessibility. Despite being designed to offer tiered, affordable care, the city has only two General Hospitals, one Central Hospital, and

no Regional Hospital, leaving higher-level services limited and unevenly distributed. At the district level, seven hospitals serve nine urban districts, while lower-tier facilities - such as 36 Subdivisional Medical Centers, six Integrated Health Centers, and three publicly run Ambulatory Health Centers - are either scarce or unevenly equipped. Most public facilities are concentrated in central or planned neighborhoods, making access difficult for residents in peripheral and informal settlements. This spatial imbalance highlights the urgent need for more equitable distribution and investment in public healthcare infrastructure across Douala.

Private sector health facilities

In Douala, private health facilities overwhelmingly dominate the urban landscape, accounting for over 90% of all health centers in the city. This dominance is not only numerical but also spatial - private clinics and polyclinics are densely concentrated in commercially active and high-income neighborhoods, leaving peripheral and informal settlements underserved. The sector is broadly divided into for-profit and non-profit components. The non-profit segment includes faith-based organizations such as the Cameroon Baptist Convention Healthcare, as well as NGOs and community associations. These facilities often deliver high-quality care, particularly in areas where public services are limited. The for-profit segment consists of commercial clinics and hospitals, including well-known institutions like the Daniel Muna Memorial Clinic and Memorial Clinic, which cater to middle- and upper-income populations.

As previously noted, private providers fall into two broad categories - non-profit and for-profit - and into formal (licensed clinics/hospitals) versus informal (unregulated) outlets.

Private For-Profit Healthcare Sector

The for-profit healthcare sector in Cameroon consists of licensed clinics, hospitals, and pharmacies operated as commercial enterprises - often by individual physicians, medical groups, or private companies. According to national data from 2020, approximately 2,535 registered for-profit health facilities were operating across the country, with a significant concentration - around 76% - located in the Centre and Littoral regions, which include the major urban centers of Yaoundé and Douala. In practice, these facilities are overwhelmingly urban, with cities like Douala hosting a dense network of private hospitals and specialty clinics. These providers function with the primary objective of generating profit, and while many offer high-quality services, their accessibility is often limited by cost, especially for low-income populations. The sector plays a dominant role in urban healthcare delivery, shaping both the availability and affordability of services in Cameroon's largest cities.

- Formal Private For-Profit Healthcare Facilities:** Formal private for-profit healthcare facilities in Douala represent a rapidly expanding segment of the city's health system. These legally registered and licensed entities include medium-to-large hospitals, polyclinics, diagnostic centers, and specialist practices, all operating with the primary goal of generating profit. Services are typically priced at market rates, making them more accessible to middle- and high-income populations. As of recent fieldwork, 469 formal private for-profit facilities were identified across Douala - a striking figure that underscores the sector's dominance and continued growth. These facilities are concentrated in commercially active and high-density neighborhoods, reflecting both demand and investment trends in urban healthcare. Notable examples include Polyclinique Bonanjo (Daniel Muna Memorial Clinic), a well-established private general hospital located in Douala's Bonanjo neighborhood. Other prominent institutions include Douala Private Hospital and specialized clinics such as La Conception, among many others. These facilities typically offer inpatient services, specialist consultations, and advanced diagnostics. Figure 9 demonstrates the geographic distribution of these 469 formal private for-profit facilities, highlighting their concentration in central and economically vibrant areas of Douala. This visualization helps reveal spatial patterns and potential gaps in access for lower-income and peripheral communities.

Figure 9: Spatial distribution of formal Private For-Profit Healthcare Facilities

- Informal Private For-Profit Healthcare Facilities:** Douala's healthcare landscape includes a growing number of informal private for-profit facilities, which operate outside formal regulatory frameworks. These facilities are typically run by nurses or paramedical staff who often assume the role of medical doctors, offering basic consultations and treatments without official licensing or oversight. Recent fieldwork identified 253 such facilities across the city Figure 10. They are commonly found in areas with limited access to formal healthcare, where affordability and proximity drive demand. These informal clinics are usually small-scale operations, set up in converted residential spaces or makeshift structures, and rely heavily on cash-based transactions. While they help fill critical service gaps, especially where public and formal private options are lacking, their unregulated nature raises concerns about the quality and safety of care. Nonetheless, they remain a vital part of Douala's health system, particularly for populations facing financial and geographic barriers.

Figure 10: Spatial distribution of informal Private For-Profit Healthcare Facilities

Private Non-Profit Healthcare Sector

This sector is made up of organizations that operate to provide healthcare services without the primary goal of making a profit. Any revenue generated is reinvested back into the organization to enhance service quality, expand access, or support community health initiatives. These institutions prioritize social impact over financial gain. This sector is largely dominated by faith-based organizations and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), which operate licensed hospitals and clinics across the country. Many are supported by churches, religious missions, or charitable foundations, and are often strategically located in areas underserved by public or commercial providers. Unlike for-profit entities, non-profit facilities do not distribute profits to owners or shareholders, and instead focus on providing affordable, quality care to vulnerable populations. Their role is especially critical in bridging healthcare gaps in remote or low-income communities, where public infrastructure may be weak and private services unaffordable.

- Formal Private Non-Profit Healthcare Facilities:** These organizations are legally registered and are often run by religious missions, charities, or non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and are structured to reinvest any revenue into improving services and expanding access - rather than generating profit. Major Christian organizations play a leading role in this sector. The Cameroon Baptist Convention Health Services (CBCHS), for example, operates a nationwide network that includes six hospitals and approximately 80 satellite clinics, according to a 2015 report. Other denominations, such as Presbyterian and Catholic missions, also maintain hospitals and clinics across the country. These facilities typically offer services at subsidized rates or are supported by donor funding, making them more accessible to underserved populations. Fieldwork identified 24 formal private non-profit healthcare facilities operating in Douala Figure 11. These facilities play a vital role in bridging healthcare gaps, especially in areas where public services are limited or where private for-profit care is unaffordable.

Figure 11: Spatial distribution of formal Private Non-Profit Healthcare Facilities

- Informal Private Non-Profit Healthcare Facilities:** This sub-sector comprises unregistered and unlicensed groups or individuals who provide free or low-cost healthcare services without formal organizational structures. These initiatives may include volunteer-run health drives, temporary clinics, mobile outreach teams, or small-scale charitable efforts organized by local actors. Their defining feature is their non-profit orientation, with services offered as a form of community support rather than commercial enterprise. In Douala, this category is extremely rare and difficult to document. Unlike formal mission hospitals or NGO-run clinics, these informal non-profit facilities are often occasional, mobile, and not easily visible in the urban landscape. Due to their transient nature and lack of fixed infrastructure, they were not counted during fieldwork, though field inquiries confirmed their existence and sporadic operation - particularly during public health campaigns or in response to local crises. Most faith-based and NGO healthcare providers in Cameroon operate within the formal sector, making informal non-profit care minimal and poorly documented. Nevertheless, its presence - however limited - reflects grassroots efforts to fill gaps in access, especially in communities underserved by both public and private systems. In summary, while Cameroon's private health sector is numerically dominated by small for-profit providers - with 94% of Douala's facilities falling into this category - formal mission hospitals and licensed non-profit clinics play a vital role in community health. The informal non-profit segment, though limited and elusive, represents an important layer of grassroots healthcare provision that warrants further attention.

Traditional Health Care in Douala: Typologies and Practices

Traditional medicine remains a deeply rooted and dynamic component of Douala's urban health system, offering both first-contact and complementary care to a wide range of residents. Recognized by Cameroon's Ministry of Public Health through its Directorate of Traditional Medicine and Pharmacy, this sector encompasses a spectrum of practices—from herbal remedies to spiritual healing—grounded in indigenous knowledge and cultural belief systems. While traditional medicine is often informal, 41 modern traditional healthcare facilities were identified in Douala that exhibit more structured operations Figure 12. These facilities stand apart from loosely organized practices and are known for treating specific conditions such as infertility, chronic pain, digestive disorders, and culturally-defined illnesses. Their presence reflects a growing formalization of traditional care, even as informal practices continue to thrive. Practitioners are spatially concentrated in urban markets like Nkoulouloun, Bépanda Double-Balle, Dakar, Ndogbassi, and the Goat Market, with additional providers dispersed across all six subdivisions. A 2019 ethnobotanical survey recorded 54 herbalists across five markets, underscoring the density and importance of these hubs. The traditional health system in Douala includes four main practitioner types:

- Herbalists** are the most visible, specializing in the preparation and sale of medicinal plants. They typically operate in busy markets and serve 10–30 clients per day, offering remedies for common ailments such as fever, digestive issues, and reproductive health problems.
- Traditional Healers** act as general practitioners of indigenous medicine, blending herbal treatments with ritual and spiritual elements. Found across all subdivisions, they often work from homes or courtyards and are sought for chronic conditions, mental health issues, and culturally-defined illnesses. Some are affiliated with professional associations like ANTRASA.
- Naturopaths** represent a modernized branch of traditional practice, combining herbal remedies with dietary and lifestyle counseling. Though fewer in number, they are gaining popularity among middle-class urban clients and typically operate from private consultation offices.
- Soothsayers** (also known as diviners or spiritualists) play a vital role in addressing the spiritual and existential dimensions of illness. Their work involves diagnosing the “hidden causes” of disease—often attributed to witchcraft, curses, or social conflict—and performing ritual healing. These practitioners are widely dispersed across neighborhoods and are frequently consulted before or after biomedical treatment, especially when conventional care fails to resolve persistent symptoms.

Figure 12: Spatial distribution of traditional Health Care in Douala

Alternative and Complementary Medicine in Douala: Landscape Overview

Alternative and Complementary Medicine (CAM) forms a dynamic and increasingly visible part of Douala's urban health ecosystem. While Cameroon officially recognizes traditional medicine in policy, there is no centralized registry for CAM providers, making it difficult to quantify their presence with precision. Many operate informally or intermittently, and small private outfits often open and close without formal documentation. Despite these challenges, fieldwork and research confirmed the presence of 26 identifiable alternative care centers in Douala, with the most structured and observable being SPAs and acupuncture clinics Figure 13. These facilities offer a range of services including tuina massage, acupuncture, cupping therapy, Chinese herbal treatments, and wellness-oriented care. Although the early 2010s saw a surge in Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) clinics, many have since downsized or closed, leaving a smaller but steady network of practitioners. SPAs have emerged as a prominent segment of Douala's wellness industry, offering services such as Swedish massage, aromatherapy, facials, hot stone therapy, and detox treatments. These centers typically operate in licensed, modern environments and cater to middle- and upper-income clients seeking relaxation and holistic care.

Other CAM modalities exist but are less visible and harder to verify: (i) Homeopathy has a limited and largely informal presence. There is no official registry, and most activity involves individual practitioners or pharmacies retailing homeopathic products. Documentation of dedicated homeopathy clinics remains sparse. (ii) Revival churches represent one of the most widespread and active forms of non-biomedical healing in Douala. Charismatic ministries regularly host healing and deliverance services, often through weekly gatherings and mass "crusades." These spiritual venues serve as key health-seeking touchpoints, especially for psychosocial and existential concerns.

Figure 13: Spatial distribution of Alternative and Complementary Medicine in Douala

4. Discussion

Low Provision Urban Areas in Douala: Low-provision urban areas in Douala - primarily informal settlements and peripheral neighborhoods - face acute healthcare deficits that mirror broader sub-Saharan patterns [14]. Public health infrastructure is overwhelmingly centralized: only seven District Hospitals serve nine urban districts, and there is roughly one public health center for every 55,245 residents [15]. As a result, peripheral populations often endure travel times exceeding an hour over poorly maintained roads, creating a pronounced “spatial deficit” that can turn minor ailments into life-threatening emergencies [16]. Economic barriers compound geographic obstacles. Ninety-four percent of Douala’s clinics are privately owned, and out-of-pocket payments account for between 66% and 72.7% of total health expenditures [17]. Low-income residents thus rely heavily on 253 informal for-profit providers - typically unlicensed nurse-run clinics - whose proximity and lower fees belie serious risks to patient safety and care quality [18, 19]. Formal non-profit centers, which should serve as a safety net for vulnerable groups, are virtually absent in these neighborhoods, further entrenching reliance on unregulated alternatives.

Moderate Provision Urban Areas in Douala: Moderate-provision zones in Douala - typically peri-central neighborhoods that lie between the affluent core and the informal periphery - offer a more varied but still uneven mix of healthcare options. At their heart are Subdivisional Medical Centers (36 in total) and the occasional District Hospital, reflecting the intermediate tier of Cameroon’s three-level health pyramid. In practice, however, these facilities differ dramatically in capacity: some possess basic diagnostic tools and stable staff, while others lack essential equipment and trained personnel. Centralized planning and resource allocation compound these gaps, as national data reveal that 70 percent of regions fall below 1.5 health workers per 1,000 population, leaving moderate-provision areas with limited access to specialized care and cumbersome referral pathways [16]. Financial barriers further constrain access. With out-of-pocket spending accounting for approximately 72.7 percent of total health expenditures, even middle-income households struggle to afford private services [20]. The fragmentation of health financing - 30 distinct schemes documented as of 2013 - adds administrative complexity and unpredictability to care-seeking. Consequently, residents routinely turn to a patchwork of small private clinics, informal providers, and traditional practitioners. Herbalists and traditional healers, concentrated around market hubs like Nkoulouloun, Bépanda Double-Balle, Dakar, and Ndogbassi, deliver first-line relief for ailments ranging from digestive disorders to chronic pain. This blend of biomedical, informal, and culturally rooted services underscores the adaptive strategies moderate-provision communities employ to navigate systemic shortcomings.

High Provision Urban Areas in Douala: Affluent central districts - most notably Akwa and Bonanjo - concentrate Douala’s premier healthcare resources. Here, residents are within easy reach of the city’s two main referral hospitals, Douala General Hospital (Category 1) and Hôpital Laquintinie (Category 2), alongside a dense network of licensed providers. Field mapping identified 469 formal private for-profit facilities in these commercial hubs, including high-end polyclinics such as Polyclinique Bonanjo, as well as well-known mission hospitals. This abundance reflects broader workforce trends: more than half of Cameroon’s health personnel are employed in the Littoral region, and similar doctor-density patterns appear within these central districts, mirroring national concentrations in Yaoundé’s Centre region (40 percent of doctors for 18 percent of the population). Yet resource wealth does not translate into universal access. The rigidly centralized health system concentrates decision-making at the national level, limiting community-based outreach and local adaptability. Financial barriers remain steep: 94 percent of Douala’s facilities are privately operated, fee structures are unregulated, and out-of-pocket payments account for approximately 66 percent of all health spending. Even residents living next door to these high-quality centers often face prohibitive costs, pushing those unable to pay into overcrowded public wards with long wait times.

The result is a two-tiered health market where premium services thrive alongside persistent inequities. High-provision areas showcase the best of Douala’s medical capabilities - but they also starkly illuminate the economic and spatial divides that leave the majority of the city’s population underserved. The map below illustrates the spatial distribution of public, private, and mission-run facilities in these high-provision districts, highlighting both resource density and the pockets of unmet need within Douala’s urban core.

Implications of Douala’s Urban Health System: Douala’s healthcare landscape, though modeled on Cameroon’s national three-tier framework, reveals a stark duality: an urban health advantage in affluent central districts and an urban health penalty in peripheral informal settlements. Central neighborhoods benefit from a dense concentration of high-tier public hospitals and licensed private clinics, while peripheral zones suffer from a pronounced “spatial deficit,” forcing residents to travel long distances - often over poor roads - to reach even basic care facilities. This geographic maldistribution deepens vulnerabilities in areas already burdened by endemic diseases such as malaria and cholera. Financial barriers further entrench these disparities. With 66 - 72.7 percent of health spending paid out-of-pocket, access to quality care is closely tied to income, effectively privileging wealthier households and marginalizing low- and middle-income residents. The predominance of private providers - 94 percent of all clinics in Douala - means that market-rate fees place formal services out of reach for many, driving the urban poor toward overcrowded public centers or unregulated informal clinics that pose safety risks. Underlying these geographic and economic hurdles is a critical health workforce shortage. Nationally, Cameroon falls below WHO’s recommended health worker density, and more than half of the country’s medical personnel are clustered in just three regions, including the Littoral (where Douala is located). Within the city, this concentration reinforces inequities: high-provision areas enjoy better staffing and specialist services, while moderate and low-provision zones grapple with understaffed centers and cumbersome referral pathways. Together, these factors perpetuate a socio-spatial gradient of health inequity in Douala. Despite hosting 17 percent of Cameroon’s health facilities, resource allocation follows economic lines rather than population need, leaving vulnerable communities reliant on fragmented, informal, or traditional care networks. Addressing this imbalance will require not only expanding regulated public and non-profit services in underserved areas but also reforming financing mechanisms and decentralizing workforce planning to ensure equitable access across all urban zones.

5. Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that the spatial distribution of healthcare facilities in Douala is marked by significant geographic inequities, shaped by the city’s rapid and unplanned urban expansion. While Douala benefits from a relatively high concentration of healthcare resources compared to rural regions, these resources are unevenly distributed, with central urban zones enjoying dense coverage and peripheral neighborhoods remaining underserved. Public sector facilities, though essential, are insufficiently aligned with population density, while

private providers dominate service delivery but are concentrated in economically advantaged areas. Traditional and alternative healthcare providers play a critical role in bridging access gaps, particularly in informal settlements. The integration of spatial analysis with qualitative insights revealed that automated GIS-based accessibility models alone are inadequate for capturing the lived realities of healthcare access in Douala. Field-based validation and community perspectives were essential in refining travel time estimates and understanding the socio-cultural dynamics influencing healthcare utilization. The findings underscore the urgent need for evidence-based urban health planning that prioritizes geographic equity. Strategic interventions should focus on expanding public healthcare infrastructure in peripheral and underserved areas, while recognizing and supporting the complementary roles of diverse provider types. Policymakers must also consider the spatial dimensions of health equity when allocating resources and designing interventions, ensuring that all residents - regardless of location or socioeconomic status - can access timely and quality care. Ultimately, this research contributes to a growing body of urban health geography literature and offers practical insights for improving healthcare provision in rapidly urbanizing African cities.

Article Information

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.), and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of manuscripts.

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